

INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT SYSTEM - PIRLS. ORGANIZATION PROCESS AND EVALUATION CRITERIA

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Abstract. In today's fast-paced era, the process of globalization in any field is one of the important factors of society's life and, in turn, leads to the development of science and technology, high growth of the economy, as well as the deepening of the process of integration in the field of education. The quality of education, the competence of personnel, the task of training competitive qualified specialists as an important factor of the socio-economic development of the country have become important features of the era of globalization. Developed countries consider the role of youth education in the development of society and human development to be important. That is why they pay special attention to the quality of education. At the same time, the concept of quality in the field of education became very popular in our country. Increasing the intellectual potential of the future young generation, forming a broad worldview is important not only for a specific country, but also for the international community. Therefore, with issues such as the quality of education and the assessment of the quality of education, many international organizations have established international standards for the assessment of education in certain applicant countries, such as PIRLS, TIMSS, PISA, TALIS, PIAAC, ICCS, SITES, IALS, ALL. implemented evaluation programs. In particular, the signing of an agreement on the participation of Uzbekistan in the PISA and PIRLS studies will create a basis for the fundamental reform of the educational system of the Republic of Uzbekistan and contribute to the development of the intellectual activity of the young generation, their competence and creativity in education. happy Today, it is very necessary to integrate such assessment programs into the educational process. You can learn more about one of these assessment programs, PIRLS, as you read the article below.

Keywords: PIRLS international evaluation program, its organization process, evaluation criteria, requirements, rating.

МЕЖДУНАРОДНАЯ СИСТЕМА ОЦЕНКИ - PIRLS. ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННЫЙ ПРОЦЕСС И КРИТЕРИИ ОЦЕНКИ

Аннотация. В современную стремительно развивающуюся эпоху процесс глобализации в любой сфере является одним из важных факторов жизни общества и, в свою очередь, приводит к развитию науки и техники, высокому росту экономики, а также углублению процесс интеграции в сфере образования. Качество образования, компетентность кадров, задача подготовки конкурентоспособных квалифицированных специалистов как важный фактор социально-экономического развития страны стали важными чертами эпохи глобализации. Развитые страны считают важной роль образования молодежи в развитии общества и человеческого потенциала. Именно поэтому они уделяют особое внимание качеству образования. В то же время понятие качества в сфере образования стало очень популярным в нашей стране. Повышение интеллектуального потенциала будущего молодого поколения, формирование широкого мировоззрения важно не только для конкретной страны, но и для мирового сообщества. Поэтому по таким вопросам, как качество образования и оценка качества образования,

многие международные организации установили международные стандарты оценки образования в определенных странах-заявителях, такие как PIRLS, TIMSS, PISA, TALIS, PIAAC, ICCS, САЙТЫ, IALS, BCE. реализованные программы оценки. В частности, подписание соглашения об участии Узбекистана в исследованиях PISA и PIRLS создаст основу для коренного реформирования системы образования Республики Узбекистан и будет способствовать развитию интеллектуальной активности подрастающего поколения, их компетентность и креативность в образовании. happy Сегодня очень необходимо интегрировать подобные оценочные программы в образовательный процесс. Вы можете узнать больше об одной из этих программ оценки, PIRLS, прочитав статью ниже.

Ключевые слова: международная программа оценки PIRLS, процесс ее организации, критерии оценки, требования, рейтинг.

In our country, in addition to current issues of state and societal importance, special attention is being paid to the issue of improving the quality of education and adequate preparation for international assessment processes. Successful participation in international assessment programs is directly related to improving the quality of education. Participation in it, not only in Uzbekistan, but also in the world community, is considered an important tool in moving from assessing whether students have memorized the curriculum to assessing their competencies, that is, their ability to apply the knowledge they have acquired at school in real life situations, to develop creative and logical thinking skills, and to evaluate it. In addition, teachers are required to enrich students' imaginations about PIRLS research, increase the level of preparation for international studies, develop students' creative and logical thinking skills, thereby contributing to the improvement of the quality of education, in cooperation with the Education Inspectorate, the National Center under it, and experts in the public education system. is being implemented.

PIRLS (Progress in International Reading Literacy Study) is an international assessment system that assesses the quality of reading and comprehension levels of primary school students in different countries. The study is conducted periodically - once every five years, and so far it has been conducted five times: in 2001, 2006, 2011, 2016 and 2021.

PIRLS enables evidence-based decision-making to improve reading instruction. States use PIRLS to:

- to monitor the trends of achievements at the level of the education system on a global scale;
- monitor the impact of new or revised education policies;
- identification of weak points of education and implementation of educational reform;
- Improving teaching and learning through research and analysis of PIRLS data;
- conducting appropriate work such as monitoring fairness or evaluating students in additional classes;
- learning to read and teach.

The PIRLS project was created under the auspices of the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA — International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement). Boston College in Chestnut Hill (Massachusetts, USA) is responsible

for organizing international studies. Preparation of assignments for international research is carried out in the data center in Hamburg, Germany.

In Uzbekistan, this study is carried out by the State Inspectorate for Quality Control of Education under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan in cooperation with the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The PIRLS international study provides an international comparison of information on the level of development of reading comprehension skills of primary school students, which can serve public policy in the field of education to improve reading and teaching. provides analysis. Currently, according to the definition of PIRLS, reading literacy is the ability to understand and use the forms of written language required by society and valued by humans, as well as the ability to create meaning from texts in various forms. The research focuses on demonstrating understanding of how to apply learned skills to new projects and situations.

The reader is an active participant in this process, creating meaning, reflecting on the text, and consciously choosing effective reading strategies. Each type of text follows typical patterns and rules to help the reader interpret the text. Any text can have different forms. These include traditional books, magazines, documents and newspapers as well as written forms in digital form.

The PIRLS study assesses student learning in two ways: in-class and out-of-school:

1. Reading in order to evaluate the student's literary experience;
2. Reading for the purpose of learning and using information.

According to the rules of the study, four groups of reading ability are assessed when reading artistic and informational texts:

- *find clearly specified information;*
- *forming conclusions;*
- *data interpretation and synthesis;*
- *analysis and evaluation of content, language features and text structure.*

Depending on the complexity of the texts in the study, the average is 500 to 800 words, 400–500 for countries with low student literacy, and about 1000 words in ePIRLS.

The content of the text is suitable for 9-10 year old students, it avoids topics that are very specific to some cultures, and it is also interesting and not very familiar to the student.

In the PIRLS study, the levels of reading literacy are described as follows:

Highest level (625 points and above) – Students can absorb a text as a whole while also understanding its individual parts in relation to each other. Can draw on the text to support his/her opinion when explaining the author's idea.

High level (550 points) - Students understand the important messages of the text, make their own conclusions based on the text, can evaluate both the content and form of the text, can pay attention to some of its linguistic features.

Intermediate level (475 points) – Students can find information from the text, draw their own conclusions based on the text using some features of text form and language.

Lower Level (400 points) – Students extract a clear message from a text that is easy to limit.

The following system is used for qualitative and quantitative assessment of work performed at PIRLS:

- correct answers in the answer selection method are evaluated with 1 point;

- correct answers regarding determining the sequence of topics are evaluated with 1 point; The PIRLS 2021 international study is considered the fifth cycle, which is a continuation of the studies conducted in 2001, 2006, 2011 and 2016 within the framework of this program. The number of countries participating in each PIRLS study is increasing. Approximately 70 countries are slated to participate in the PIRLS 2021 international survey, including benchmark participants and many others that have participated in previous cycles since 2001. With each evaluation cycle, the PIRLS research scope is updated, allowing participating countries to share their new ideas and the latest information on their curricula, standards, scopes and guidelines. This allows the scopes to be educationally appropriate, increases the interdependence of each assessment process, and serves to further refine the scopes, assignments, and procedures. In the international PIRLS 2021 survey, the coverage areas will be updated using the guidelines outlined in the PIRLS 2021 encyclopedia, a study study, and information collected through reviews by selected National Research Coordinators (NRCs) from participating countries. In the PIRLS international assessment program held in 2021, among about 70 countries, the 4th graders of our country also participated for the first time. The results of the study will be published in December 2022.

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